

MENTAL BANKS, MENTAL BOOKS, AND MENTAL STATES OF OUR MIND

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My previous article on noötherapy (Fall 2007 issue of *Unlimited Human!*) has attracted numerous emails and calls from interested readers asking me for more. In that issue, I discussed the operating definition and the basic concept of mind, and then went on to elaborate the nine mental states of mind. In this short article, I shall address two other important issues relating to noös or the mind: (1) mental storage-and-retrieval banks, or simply known as mental banks; and (2) mental books, which refer to perception, cognition, meta-cognition, affection, and volition (see Figure 1). Then I shall briefly explain how mental banks, mental books, and mental states of mind can be applied in our professional work as counselors and therapists.

Figure 1

MENTAL BANKS

When we talk about mental storage and retrieval of information, the word bank comes to mind. Call it mental bank (also known as memory), there are three mental banks of mind: working memory, short-term memory and long-term memory. Markova and Powell (1992) defined working memory as the conscious mode of mind that organizes incoming information; short-term memory as the subconscious mode that sorts out information; and long-term memory as the unconscious mode that stores and retrieves information as and when it is needed (see Figure 2).

Figure 2

The conscious working memory sets us alert and awake, gets us to pay attention to what goes on around us, absorbs incoming information as well as expresses our views, and helps to organize details to make logical sense and state our points clearly.

The short-term memory subconsciously helps us sort incoming information, makes us aware of both the input we get from the outside world and our inner frame of reference, helps us move from alertness into deep relaxation, and from relaxation into active self-expression. Understanding how this mode works enables a hypnotherapist to know how and why hypnotherapy works.

The long-term memory functions at the unconscious level to help us to integrate what we learn (new information) with what we have already known (prior knowledge). This is known as schema-matching. According to Markova and Powell (1992), “Memories are brought to mind and connections are made on a very deep level. This way of thinking is designed to make patterns by arranging and re-arranging experience in many ways and communicating the way things could be.” (p. 38) This unconscious mode also devotes to creating messages indirectly through dreams, symbols, imagery, analogy, in many directions simultaneously. This is the mental domain which opens to the practice of alternative therapies such as dream therapy, diagnostic/expressive art therapy, psychotherapy, and hypnotherapy.

MENTAL BOOKS

Whatever that can be found in the mental banks (or memories) are the essential mental books. By mental books, I

refer to the five key mental bases: perception, cognition, meta-cognition, affection, and volition (see Figure 3). Let us examine each of these very briefly.

Figure 3

- Perception is defined as “the process of knowing objects and objective events by means of the senses” (Chaplin, 1985, p.330). It begins with attention, which is the process of selectively observing the environment around us. This involves the conscious mode of the working memory.
- Cognition is defined as the process of “embracing all forms of knowing that include imagining, reasoning and judging” (Chaplin, 1985, p.85). It involves schema-matching between the subconscious and unconscious modes of our memories.
- Meta-cognition is defined as the higher level of cognitive process that involves monitoring and understanding what goes on in cognition, e.g., understanding what is to be understood. This involves the unconscious mode of the long-term memory.
- Chaplin (1985) defined affection “as a broad class of mental processes, including feeling, emotion, moods, and temperament” (p.14). It evokes emotions in response to current and/or past experiences and also involves current-past experience-matching that takes place between the subconscious and conscious modes of our memories.
- Volition refers to the will or the process of deciding upon a course of action (Chaplin, 1985). This involves the conscious mode of the working memory and the outcome is an observable behavior.

Concrete and/or abstract concept formation takes place at the point of interaction among perception, cognition and affection so that either a concrete concept (e.g., “horse” or “train”) or an abstract concept (e.g., “love” or “democracy”) will be analyzed and synthesized to make sense to our mind for the purpose of meaningful storage as well as retrieval for future use. Meta-cognition and volition also play an important role in concept formation by application and trial (i.e., hypothesis-testing) in a real situation to confirm if it is what it is.

As we can see, our mind is made of three mental banks consisting of the five key mental books. The complexity of mind does not stop there. It is further divided into nine mental states which have already been discussed in my previous article.

Our next concern is how to apply what we know about the mental banks, mental books, and mental states of mind in our professional work as counselors and therapists.

A BRIEF NOTE ON PRACTICAL APPLICATION

As a counselor and therapist, I have met all kinds of clients and dealt with them differently because they experience different kinds of problems. Hence, I need to understand them better through a careful examination of their mental banks, mental books, and their mental states of mind during my therapy sessions with them.

To understand each mind, I need to know what goes through the client's mental banks or memories (i.e., from the working memory via the short-term memory to the long-term memory and then vice-versa), and how the external stimulus he/she has experienced affects his/her view (perception) which might in turn trigger the internal stimulus that causes the client to think/reason (cognition) in a certain way before he/she acts (volition) according to the way he/she feels (affection) and at the same time, thinks and/or re-thinks (meta-cognition) basing on what he/she presumes he/she has understood in response to the situation in which he/she encounters. When the client shares about his/her feelings and/or thoughts, I need to listen attentively to him/her in order to know from which mental states of mind he/she is speaking.

Through constant practice, I have grown and become more experienced in using mental banks, mental books, and mental states of mind to analyze and synthesize my clients' inputs and outputs during the sessions they spent with me. Perhaps in the near future, I shall share more about how to conduct a noötherapy session properly and to incorporate it into counseling and hypnotherapy.

Finally, it is important for me to stress here that all the figures shown in this article should not in any way be regarded as a realistic picture of any part of the mind they are attempting to represent. Boxes or circles have been used, but they could equally well have been shown in any other shapes. Their purpose is to provide an analogy, and the exact representation is a matter of convenience.

REFERENCES

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- Markova, D., and Powell, A.R. (1992). Your child is smart; A new approach to learning. New York, NY: MJF Books.

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